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The Platform for Sharing, Initiating and Learning Citizen Science in Europe

Deliverable 1.1, Data Management Plan

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1 Version Log

Version	Date	Released by	Nature of Change
DRAFT	18/06/2019	Katherin Wagenknecht (MfN)	Initial Draft for Discussion in Consortium
DRAFT v2	27/06/2019	Katherin Wagenknecht (MfN)	Internal review by Consortium Members/Executive Board
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1.1	11/07/2019	Katherin Wagenknecht (MfN)	Final Review Executive Board

2 Definitions and Acronyms

CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
Data	Information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. The focus is on research data that is available in digital form. (European Commission, 2016)
Dataset	A grouping of data
Digital Curation	Selection, preservation, maintenance and archiving of electronically stored data
DMP	Data Management Plan
DS	Data Set
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
Metadata	A description of data
MoRRI	Monitoring the evolution and benefits of responsible research and innovation
Open Access	Access that is free to all and free of any restrictions
Open Data	Data that can be freely used, shared and built on by anyone for any purpose
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe

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PPSR	Public Participation in Scientific Research
Repository	A location in which data is stored or managed
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals

3 Executive Summary

The EU-Citizen.Science Data Management Plan (DMP) is Deliverable 1.1 (D1.1) from the coordination and support action (CSA), EU-Citizen.Science, grant agreement (GA) 824580. This deliverable introduces the first version of the DMP. The DMP describes the way in which the EU-Citizen.Science consortium will manage the datasets that will emerge from the project, and how best practice in terms of metadata and archiving will be used to ensure that the data will be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) for other potential users. Such users include researchers and practitioners in the field of citizen science, as well as any other interested party, in accordance with the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data pilot. Further, the DMP provides information about what datasets the consortium is aiming to preserve and in which format.

The aim of this document is to lay out the preliminary DMP for the project. The purpose of the document is to put in place the definitions, explanations and details that will facilitate the potential reuse of the data that will be collected during the project. The DMP will allow this data to be in accordance with the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data pilot. The report is addressing the following issues:

- 1) How EU-Citizen.Science will manage datasets
- 2) How data will be made findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.

4 Introduction

The purpose of the preliminary Data Management Plan (DMP) for the EU-Citizen.Science project is to put in place the details and definitions that will facilitate the potential reuse of the data collected and processed within the project. The DMP will ensure that this data will be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), in accordance with the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data pilot.

4.1 Project Background

The EU-Citizen.Science project is supported by the European Commission under its Horizon 2020 programme *Science with and for Society* (SwafS). The project will develop and maintain an innovative, collaborative online hub that will serve as the nexus for bringing together a

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vibrant European Citizen Science community. This shared online space for exchange and learning aims to transform the way that citizen science projects are conceived and developed, as it encourages and supports citizen science novices, practitioners, participants and institutions equally. Here, the European Citizen Science community will be able to exchange experiences and successful strategies to jointly advance the role and recognition of citizen science in the European context. The EU-Citizen.Science project will take stock of the vast amount of already-existing tools, guidelines and other materials available on citizen science, to highlight, curate and organize high-quality contents for an ever growing and diversifying group of stakeholders.

The Consortium of EU-Citizen.Science consists of the following 14 partners:

Partner Acronym	Partner	Organisation Type	Country
MfN	Museum für Naturkunde Berlin	Museum	Germany
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association	Association	Germany
IIASA	Internationales Institut für Angewandte Systemanalyse	Research Institution	Austria
Earthwatch	Earthwatch	Non-profit organization	United Kingdom
UCL	University College London	Research Institution	United Kingdom
ECSITE	Ecsite	International non-profit organization under Belgian jurisdiction	Belgium
ZSI	Zentrum für soziale Innovationen	Research Institution	Austria
TCD	Trinity College Dublin	Research Institution	Ireland
VA	Vetenskap & Allmänhet	Non-profit civil society organisation	Sweden
NHM	Natural History Museum	Museum	United Kingdom
ULEI	Universiteit Leiden	Research Institution	Netherlands

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MRU	Mykolo Romerio Universitetas	Research Institution	Lithuania
MFCR	Município de Figueira de Castelo Rodrigo	Policy-making organisation	Portugal
MINECO	MINECO-FECYT (Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities)	Policy-making organisation	Spain
BOKU	Universität für Bodenkultur Wien	Research Institution	Austria
IRSNB	Institut royal des Sciences naturelles de Belgique	Natural History Museum and Research Institution	Belgium
UTARTU	Tartu Ülikool	Research Institution	Belgium
MNHM	Museum National D'histoire Naturelle	Natural History Museum	France
AUTH	Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis	Research Institution	Greece
ESSRG	ESSRG Kft.	Research Institution	Hungary
FGC	Fondazione Grosseto Cultura (Museo di Storia Naturale della Maremma)	Natural History Museum	Italy
IberCivis	Fundación Ibercivis	Foundation	Spain

Table 1, Overview of Consortium

Work packages No	Description	Lead partner	Contribution partner
WP 1 (MfN)	Coordination and Management	MfN	All partners
WP 2 (ECSA)	Platform, Community and Network Building	ECSA	All partners and third parties
WP 3 (IIASA)	Content - Framework, Quality Assurance and Curation	IIASA	MFN, ECSA, Earthwatch, ZSI, UCL, TCD, NHM, MRU, MINECO, IberCivis

WP 4 (Earthwatch)	Awareness and Engagement- Public and Policy Makers	Earthwatch	MFN, ECSA, UCL, ECSITE, TCD, VA, NHM, ULEI, MRU, MFCR, MINECO and third parties
WP 5 (UCL)	Training Needs Assessment, Creation and Delivery	UCL	All partners and third parties
WP 6 (ECSITE)	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Strategic Communication	ECSITE	MFN, ECSA, IIASA, Earthwatch, UCL, TCD, VA, NHM, ULEI, MRU, MFCR, MINECO, FGC, IRNSB
WP 7 (ZSI)	Evaluation and Impact Assessment	ZSI	MFN, ECSA, IIASA, Earthwatch, UCL, MINECO
WP 8 (MfN)	Ethic requirements	MFN	MFN

Table 2, Overview of work packages, titles and leading beneficiaries

The following provides a short description of the work packages:

WP 1 Coordination and Management

The main objective of WP 1 is to ensure a well-planned, cost-efficient project management, including consortium coordination and financial and administrative management. The main tasks of the work package are (a) Administrative and financial Management, (b) Coordination of project partners and cooperation with EC representatives, (c) Monitoring impact, ethical issues, gender balance and inclusiveness, (d) Cooperation with winning RIA projects and other EU-funded projects.

WP 2 Platform, Community and Network Building

The central aim of this work package is to co-design and implement the online platform that will serve as a mutual space for learning, knowledge-sharing, training and support for the European citizen science community. The platform (1) enables citizen scientists, and practitioners to exchange experiences and successful strategies, (2) identifies good practices that incentivize career scientists to engage with citizen science activities, (3) strengthens networks and co-ordination among citizen science projects across Europe. The core structure of the EU-Citizen.Science platform includes (a) mapping and community functionality such as individual & institutional profiles, discussion forums, news boards, and a calendar of events; (b) knowledge management functionality to support the uploading and structured sharing of tools, guidelines and roadmaps, (c) a structured repository of best practice across the project life-cycle; (d) sign-posting to external sources, networks and institutions, (e) project search functionality with metadata.

WP 3 Content - Framework, Quality Assurance and Curation

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WP3 will develop a content framework to identify and facilitate the collection and sharing of suitable high-quality tools, guidelines, and other materials stemming from best practices in citizen science following an inclusive, community-centred approach. Tools, guidelines, and other materials (TGMs) range from written texts, diagrams and guidelines (e.g. pdfs), to online toolkits (e.g. websites) to videos and podcasts, to software tools (e.g. Open Data Kit).

The two main objectives of WP3 are to (1) deliver organising criteria and a quality roadmap that enable citizen science practitioners and initiatives to share TGMs from best practices online, and (2) curate state of the art TGMs for engaging with, or starting citizen science activities. The TGMs will be useful to actors inexperienced in organizing and supporting citizen science initiatives as well as to career scientists, policy makers and other stakeholders.

WP 4 Awareness and Engagement – the Public and Policy Makers

This WP aims to demonstrate a conceptual model for awareness, empowerment and engagement in citizen science and for implementing citizen science across Europe. This will be done within existing citizen science initiatives (citizen science associations and networks, citizen observatories and citizen science projects) at the national and international level. Already ongoing activities will be used to demonstrate how citizen science can engender extensive, long-term and global participation across Europe by (a) using novel approaches for citizen engagement and (b) improving knowledge transfer and capacity building through the formation of national/local leaders to strengthen local-community networks.

The main objectives of WP4 are (1) to develop tools and strategies for citizen engagement, (2) to achieve increased awareness on policy issues, thanks to the provision of a collaborative tool for the engagement of citizens (the mutual learning platform), (3) to foster a consistent approach to citizen science across citizen science initiatives, (4) to leverage the commitment to policy issues of community-networks involved in the consortium, (5) to encourage policy makers to facilitate, synthesise, translate and communicate citizen science to inform societal action.

WP 5 Training Needs Assessment, Creation and Delivery

This work package acts in close partnership with WP2 and WP3, building on existing knowledge and resources to deliver an innovative new training programme for citizen science. The training is designed for the four target groups, which were noted in the call text: the public, practitioners, academia, policy makers and civil servants, press, and SMEs and industry. The focus is on train the trainer, enhancing the capacity and effectiveness of those that will train people interesting in doing citizen science.

The main objectives of WP5 are to (1) assess the training needs of those inexperienced in citizen science, (2) aggregate, curate, and create a suite of high-qualitative training resources to address these needs and enhance European knowledge-sharing in this area, (3) develop workflows to increase linkages with SDGs, (4) identify and develop a delivery model that reaches people doing citizen science and potential practitioners/citizen science project leaders in all countries

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of Europe. This work package and the resulting training programme will increase the skills and competences in citizen science practice, facilitating both scientific excellence and high-quality engagement. It will create the resources, frameworks and practitioners network that will allow the lessons from the training to continue beyond the project. This WP will actively involve Third Parties and supporters, therefore it will have an EU-wide outreach.

WP 6 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Strategic Communication

The overall goal of this WP is to engage diverse actors and stakeholders in the project activities at the local, national and EU level. Here, Citizen Science will be the buzz- and keyword for the dissemination activities. This WP will design and implement an effective communication and dissemination strategy, developing tools and measures to promote the project's activities and results to a wide spectrum of audiences, with a special focus on the general public. Furthermore, it will design and implement an effective exploitation strategy, promoting the project's results and outputs to make them widely available in the citizen science community. To reach these objectives, the WP will disseminate the results of the project to key audiences following the quadruple helix stakeholder approach. Customised strategies will be used for the diverse targets (building up from 2.2.3 Table 3), which include policymakers, intermediaries, researchers, practitioners, journalists, educators, citizen scientists, science communicators, and citizens. This WP will also ensure that all engagement and dissemination activities are interlinked and mutually reinforcing, in accordance with the project's communication strategy.

WP 7 Evaluation and Impact Assessment

The main aim of this work package is to investigate and provide evidence for whether the project attains its envisioned impact, according to the set objectives of the project. It will clearly communicate to the citizen science stakeholders of Europe how the project contributes, amongst other aspects, to the growth and identity-building of the European Citizen Science community. The indicators chosen to measure the impact of the project will be compliant with, and complementary to, existing work: such as indicators for Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), which have been recently elaborated in the MoRRI project; the Sustainable Development Goals; or specific citizen science indicators that address also wider societal goals. On the one hand, the evaluation will assess the usefulness and user-acceptance of the project activities, such as the provided trainings in WP5, the community building actions in WP2, the interaction on the EU-Citizen.Science platform, etc. to allow an iterative improvement of specific actions and instruments. On the other hand, the impact assessment will concern the overall performance of the project and its impact on the involved communities and beyond. The assessment will provide evidence based on data collected within the project, relating the data to potential longer-term aspects of shaping citizen science from different socio-political angles

WP 8 Ethic requirements

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This work package contains documentation of the consortium data protection procedures and ethical guidelines of the project. The work package sets out the ethics requirements that the project must comply with which are included as deliverables of the work package.

4.2 Data Management Plan Objectives

This document is an initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the EU-Citizen.Science project. The DMP identifies the datasets that will be generated and used during the project with respect to each work package, and defines each dataset's purpose and life cycle. The project itself aims to mainstream citizen science on a European level by creating a central hub providing tools, guidelines and materials addressing newcomers as well as relevant actors in the field of citizen science. This means there is mainly personal data being handled within the project.

In accordance with Guidelines on FAIR Data management in Horizon 2020 (European Commission, 2016), the objectives of the DMP are:

- To identify the datasets that the EU-Citizen.Science CSA will produce;
- To define how these datasets will be made 'FAIR' (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable);
- To define the allocation of resources (costs and responsibility) for data management during and after the project;
- To define procedures for data security (including data recovery as well as safe storage) during the project and for long term preservation.

The Deliverable 1.1 "Data management plan" is part of work package 1 "Coordination and Management", and has been developed following the Horizon 2020 guidelines, with additional guidelines from DMPonline as suggested by the European Commission. The DMP is intended to be a living document where information will be continuously added and revised as the implementation progresses.

A key element of sustainable data management, the DMP outlines what, and how, data will be collected, processed and/or generated, which methodology and standards will be applied, whether data will be shared/made open access and also how data will be curated and preserved during and after the end of the project. It provides guidelines, answers to issues, and presents the approach that the EU-Citizen.Science project will adopt with respect to the management and protection of data. Legal and ethical issues related to the project's collecting and/or processing of personal data are identified and practically considered, taking into consideration the different methods by which data are collected (interview, online survey, workshop, questionnaire etc.).

An updated version of the Data Management Plan will be released if other kinds of data will be generated/collected, if changes in consortium policies or in consortium composition occur, and

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if any other external factors affect the validity of the present DMP. It will be updated whenever significant changes arise, such as (but not limited to):

- New kinds of data
- Changes in consortium policies
- Changes in consortium composition

With regards to personal data, the Consortium shall ensure that data on individuals are transmitted and used in a secure environment; that the use of the data complies with ethical and legal requirements (including signed informed consent and applicable data protection laws); and that the use of both existing and new data is agreed with the data owner/data provider. Data records containing personal data are managed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679). The GDPR is a regulation by which the European Parliament, the European Council and the European Commission intend to strengthen and harmonise data protection for individuals within the European Union (EU).

The intended audience for this DMP is primarily constituted by the project partners. This document should be read in conjunction with deliverables D8.1 and D8.2. D 8.3 and D 8.4 which examine the use of the data in conjunction with the EU Data Protection Policy and the ethical use of data, respectively; this document is therefore restricted purely to the mechanics of the data management.

It is the responsibility of every partner to notify the coordinator of changes in the data they are collecting during the project.

5 Project Data

5.1 Datasets Identified

Dataset name and Outline of Data	Institution in Charge	WP
DS_EU-CITSCI_1_Project_Partner This dataset consists of consortium members, members of advisory board subscribers to mailing list, participants	MfN	1
DS_EU-CITSCI_2_Involves_Participants This dataset consists of subscribers to mailing list and participants to events	MfN/ ECSITE	1/6

DS_EU-CITSCI_3_Project_Output This dataset consists of project outputs, such as deliverables, which are not research data, but is included within this organisation of data due to reasons of completeness.	MFN	1
DS_EU-CITSCI_4_Stakeholder_Mapping This dataset consists of information about Stakeholder, key networks and platform-community members.	ECSA	2
DS_EU-CITSCI_5_User_Expectations This dataset consists of user expectations concerning the platform EU-Citizen.Science.	ECSA	2
DS_EU-CITSCI_6_TGMs This dataset consists of user expectations concerning the platform EU-Citizen.Science.	IIASA	3
DS_EU-CITSCI_7_Policy_Recommendation This dataset consists of guidelines and recommendation for policy makers.	Earthwatch	4
DS_EU-CITSCI_8_Training_Moduls This dataset consists of materials and data on training modules.	UCL	5
DS_EU-CITSCI_9_Communication This dataset consists of communication and dissemination materials.	ECSITE	6
DS_EU-CITSCI_10_Evaluation_Impact_Assessment This dataset consists of data about validation of the projects impact at multi levels.	ZSI	7

Table 3 Overview of datasets within EU-Citizen.Science

5.2 Summary of the Data

5.2.1 State the purpose of the data collection

The purpose of the data collection is on the one hand to establish an information and communication network at European level, on the other hand to identify training needs and other needs concerning Citizen Science, and how to address them. Other datasets collected will be relevant to the project communication and evaluation activities.

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5.2.2 Explain the relation to the objectives of the project

The Consortium will develop the EU-Citizen.Science platform to enable the acquisition of skills, competences, and scientific excellence amongst citizen scientists as well as practitioners, both via the knowledge hub and via the delivery of training. EU- Citizen.Science will build a platform that can be sustained and supported beyond the end of project, and that will promote the implementation of community engagement and high-quality training activities in an effective way, to ensure that it will scale as citizen science grows. The EU-Citizen.Science project will develop and maintain an innovative, collaborative online hub that will serve as the centerpiece for bringing together a vibrant European Citizen Science community. This shared online exchange and learning space will transform the way that citizen science projects are conceived and developed, encourage and support citizen science novices, practitioners, participants and institutions equally to exchange experiences, successful strategies and to jointly advance the role and recognition of citizen science in the European context. Furthermore, through collaboration channels, dialogue spaces and networking tools, the online hub will provide coordination support between new citizen science initiatives and established networks of citizen science projects. There are five main objectives of the project, for which the data is needed in different contexts and framings:

(1) Establish EU-Citizen.Science as the community hub for high-quality citizen science exchange and learning in Europe. The EU-Citizen.Science project will develop and maintain an innovative, collaborative online hub that will serve as the centerpiece for bringing together a vibrant European Citizen Science community. This shared online exchange and learning space will transform the way that citizen science projects are conceived and developed, encourage and support citizen science novices, practitioners, participants and institutions equally to exchange experiences, successful strategies and to jointly advance the role and recognition of citizen science in the European context. Furthermore, through collaboration channels, dialogue spaces and networking tools, the online hub will provide coordination support between new citizen science initiatives and therefore established a network of citizen science projects. The design and development of the platform will follow the latest principles in web design including an agile, iterative approach and focus on enabling audience and user heterogeneity, ensuring platform sustainability beyond the lifetime of this funding, maximising usability and user experience as well as expanding connectivity.

(2) Consolidate the citizen Science knowledge base and celebrate outstanding practices and state of the art in citizen science in Europe. The EU-Citizen.Science project will take stock of the vast amount of existing tools, guidelines and other materials available in and for citizen science, to highlight, curate and organise high-quality contents for an ever growing and diversifying group of interested parties. The project will enable community-driven content sharing via the online platform as well as curate and promote outstanding, state of the art tools and materials. Identifying and promoting best practices and tools will help, for example, incentivize career scientists to engage with citizen science activities, encourage citizens to join or start citizen science initiatives as well as inspire policy makers to integrate citizen science in

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local governance projects. By leveraging the unique expertise within this consortium and our associated networks, the project will ensure that the vast existing knowledge in the domain of citizen science in Europe is integrated into a roadmap and clear criteria that enable citizen science practitioners and initiatives to implement and drive forward innovation and best practices in citizen science, for maximum benefit across all stakeholders, disciplines, languages and objectives. Close collaboration and links with other SwafS and RIA citizen science projects will further place EU-Citizen.Science at the forefront of citizen science knowledge creation.

(3) Empower diverse stakeholders to become `citizen scientists`, start citizen science

initiatives, and adopt citizen science approaches professionally The EU-Citizen.Science project will provide training and learning opportunities for different stakeholder groups, primarily addressing actors inexperienced in citizen science, for example: - Citizens and actors in the general public, to start citizen science initiatives; - Actors in policy making, to enhance citizen science and adopt citizen science methodologies in participatory governance; - Career scientists, to engage in and benefit from citizen science and run citizen science projects; - Educators, to use citizen science in their educational practice; - SMEs and start-ups, to develop new scientific tools, services and business models in citizen science. To achieve this, the project will capitalise on the extensive communication and education expertise within the consortium and its networks (in particular ECSA and Ecsite). There is already extensive knowledge about training needs across different stakeholder groups that emerged from a range of projects, including EU funded Citizen Observatories, and dedicated projects that utilise citizen science such as Doing it Together Science (DITOs), Starts4All, Citizen Cyberlab, EveryAware, Citizen Sense, D-NOSES and many others. Therefore, this objective will focus on addressing those needs thorough optimum training methodologies for the different audiences and organising material from across the field of citizen science into training modules. Essential gaps in training materials will be addressed through the development of novel training resources. At least 20 training modules will be developed, tested, and disseminated across all EU countries.

(4) Exploring new pathways for participatory governance, by strengthening links between citizen science and policy making

The EU-Citizen.Science project recognises the importance of informed decisions and the differences between the scientific and policy-making processes. The project will emphasise the roles of facilitating, synthesising, translating, and communicating citizen science to inform societal action. Its concepts are applicable to a broad range of practitioners and policy-makers worldwide. Creating social change and solving societal problems requires both knowledge and power. Citizen scientists have knowledge, but typically limited authority to drive change behaviour. Policy-makers have power but may lack in-depth knowledge of particular problems. Linking these two groups, and intermediaries from civil society, brings knowledge together with power to make informed decisions that can drive social change. The project will explore new pathways for participatory governance through scoping of and addressing mutual information needs, capacity building, development of partnerships for joint planning, fundraising and project implementation, and direct engagement through discussions and joint activities. With these aims the project will build on the pioneering

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activities of policy engagement in citizen science to foster RRI as realised currently in the DITOs project as well as other initiative in this space, e.g. the VOICES and CIMULACT projects. This objective will be accomplished through the multi-level engagement model and WP4: Awareness and Engagement - Public and Policy Makers, led by Earthwatch.

(5) Advance citizen science into the mainstream of public engagement and science, communication and education The EU-Citizen.Science project will create a step-change in overall awareness of citizen science among the general public, expand and improve communication between citizen science and science journalism, as well as accelerate uptake of citizen science in formal and informal education. A multitude of local multiplier, engagement and awareness events will be organised and delivered utilizing existing events, such as the European Researchers' Night, as well as the far reach and diverse spread of the project consortium, networks and Third Parties. Ecsite and Earthwatch will especially capitalise on their links with formal and informal education to further promote and raise awareness about citizen science and how educators can actively engage in citizen science projects. In addition, particular efforts will be taken to establish close ties with science journalists, to accompany projects from the start, as well as to support the formation of a citizen science journalist network via the EU- Citizen.Science platform. This cross-cutting objective will be tackled within WP4: Awareness and Engagement - Public and Policy Makers and WP6: Dissemination, Exploitation and Strategic Communication.

5.2.3 Specify the types and formats of data generated

Type of data:

- Personal data
 - Names
 - Affiliation
 - Countries
 - Mailing addresses
 - Professional background
 - Job titles
 - Gender
 - IP addresses
 - Photos

- Other data
 - Data from questionnaires
 - Data from tutorials
 - Data from workshops about training needs/expectations/etc

Formats of the data:

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- Data and metadata will be requested, stored and transferred in comma-separated values CSV format
- To facilitate the data exchange, MS Excel compatible files including comma separated and .xls(x) format will be also accepted.
- For statistical purposes, other formats include .sas7bdat (SAS), .RData (R), .SAV (SPSS), .mat (matlab).
- Where applicable data formats may be migrated when new technologies become available and are proved robust enough to ensure digital continuity and continued availability of data.

5.2.4 Specify if existing data is being reused

No existing data is being re-used.

5.2.5 Specify the origin of the data

Origin of the data:

- Data from sign-up sheets at workshops
- Data from questionnaires
- Data submitted to surveys
- Data from tutorials
- Data from web servers
- Data submitted by subscription to the newsletter
- Data from interviews

5.2.6 State the expected size of the data

To be evaluated during the course of the project. The expected size depends on the extend and the nature of the data that are made available.

5.2.7 Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

The above-mentioned data could be useful to

- EU-Citizen.Science consortium;
- European Commission services and European Agencies; European community of Citizen Science;
- Stakeholder groups as identified within the proposal (politician makers, researcher, citizens etc.).

6 FAIR Data

This section is written using the standard H2020 template for FAIR data given in the Guidelines on FAIR Data management in Horizon 2020 (European Commission, 2016).

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6.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

6.1.1 Outline the discoverability/identifiability of data (metadata provision)

All data will have an associated metadata document (stored as a .txt file) which describes key aspects of the data, as defined in Annex 1- Metadata to be recorded against each Dataset.

6.1.2 Outline naming conventions used

Event listings are stored in a central spreadsheet and individual events are assigned a unique identifier of the format [short name partner]_[date]

Project deliverables are assigned a unique identifier EU-Citizen.Science_[number of Deliverable]_[date of submission], e.g. EU-Citizen.Science_D8.1 H-POPD_26062019 (already submitted).

All files made publicly available reference EU-Citizen.Science in their name, with the recommendation that the convention EU-Citizen.Science_xxxxxxx_[date], where xxxxxxx is a meaningful short description of the file.

Photographs and audio/visual recordings are be named EU-Citizen.Science_[event]_[date of event]_[description of event/photograph content, e.g. workshop/dinner/group meeting].

6.1.3 Outline the approach towards search keyword

We provide search keywords for optimizing possibilities for re-use

6.1.4 Outline the approach for clear versioning

Filenames will include creation date in YYYYMMDD format. Deliverable reports will have a data identification sheet and version log.

6.1.5 Specify standards for metadata creation

Every Dataset will have an associated text document with its associated metadata. An appropriate scheme is being developed and evaluated during course of time.

6.2 Making data openly accessible

6.2.1 Specify which data will be made openly available

The only data which will not be made openly accessible will be data which contains personally identifiable information (e.g. individual evaluation forms). These will be summarised and any individual forms used for research publications (such as inclusion in ‘user stories’) will be redacted or anonymised before online storage.

With reference to the differentiation already introduced in Chapter 2.3 Types of data between personal data and other research data collected and processed in the project, this question of the provision and publication of research data must now also be answered. The personal data processed in the project are not made publicly accessible, but kept closed and inaccessible to third parties.

Personal data will not be openly accessible, nor available to third parties to guarantee participants’ privacy. Visual materials including personal data or personal images that can endanger participants’ privacy will not be made publicly available, unless the provide written consent. The original recordings and artefacts will not be made publicly available due, respectively, to personal data protection reasons, and to practical issues. Both single questionnaires and single transcriptions will not be made publicly accessible as Open Research Data (ORD). Transcriptions and questionnaires will be stored on secure space by relevant WP leaders. In any case, personal data, such as names and e-mail addresses, will never be made publicly available for protecting users’ privacy.

6.2.2 Specify how the data will be made available

During the project, a subset of summary data (e.g. event visitor statistics and feedback summaries) will be made accessible by one or more methods below:

- Via newsletters, reports and other publications on the platform;
- Via partner’s local websites;
- Via social media.

Detailed data will be available to all consortium partners via the project’s shared drive (with the exception of individual questionnaires, which will be stored at each partner’s premises), the access to this drive is restricted to project partners. Should other individuals wish to access the data for research purposes during the project, it will be openly shared on request. At the end of the project, data to be preserved (as identified in section 4.1) will be stored in a suitable data repository. As projects repository the Executive Board agreed on using ZENODO.

6.2.3 Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data

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Data will be published using standard file formats (txt, pdf, csv etc.). All data will be accessed using standard tools. Software relevant to access the data would be made available, but it is not seen as being a requirement. Should it be needed we will provide the required open source to access and analyse the data.

6.2.4 Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited

For the duration of the project, personal data will be stored on local secured server the partner responsible takes care of. Data to be public, like curated TGMs and other outcomes of the project are stored on a central drive, on the project's platform and on [ZENODO](#).

6.2.5 Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions

At this stage, no restrictions are envisaged; should it be required, the appropriate open software will be provided to access the data or export the data to standard formats.

6.3 Making data interoperable

Information relating to the interoperability of datasets has been collated in the table about the dataset details chapter 11. As the project progresses and data is identified and collected, further information on making data interoperable will be outlined in subsequent versions of the DMP. In specific, information on data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodology to follow to facilitate interoperability and whether the project uses standard vocabulary for all data types present to allow interdisciplinary interoperability.

6.3.1 Access the interoperability of your data, specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards you will follow to facilitate interoperability

In the project we use standard file formats as noted above. Every dataset will have metadata. For all types of data present in our data we use standard vocabularies according to PPSR_CORE, which was developed for research on and with citizen science. (<https://www.wilsoncenter.org/article/ppsr-core-metadata-standards>).

6.3.2 Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-

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disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

For all types of data present in our data we use standard vocabularies according to PPSR_CORE, which was developed for research on and with citizen science. (<https://www.wilsoncenter.org/article/ppsr-core-metadata-standards>). In the unlikely case of using uncommon vocabulary or to generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, we will provide mapping of ontology and vocabulary.

6.4 Making data re-usable

6.4.1 Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible

It is planned that CC Licenses will be used for all data to be preserved. Since these are different data types, different licensing will also apply. Which licenses will be granted in individual cases will be determined during the course of the project work.

6.4.2 Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

This section will be compiled throughout the course of the project, when we get more information on the datasets that are made available for EU-Citizen.Science.

It is not envisaged that the project will publish or seek patents. The data collected and analysed during the project will be made openly available at the end of the project.

6.4.3 Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

All Personal Identifiable Information will be restricted to internal usage and not going to be shared with third parties. For shared information, standard format, open source software, and proper documentation will guarantee re-usability by third parties.

6.4.4 Describe data quality assurance processes

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A quality assurance process is to be installed within the duration of the project.

6.4.5 Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

5 years (for another five years after the end of the project in December 2021, the continuation of the platform is ensured, under the responsibility of ECSA)

7 Allocation of resources

7.1 Estimate the costs for marking your data FAIR

ZENODO is free so no additional costs for its usage is expected. Data will be uploaded by the Museum für Naturkunde as Coordinator and as part of WP 6 dissemination activities, therefore with the support of ECSITE. More specifically, deliverables and publications will be uploaded no later than 3 months after release or whenever we have the Ok from the reviewers, whereas datasets will be uploaded at the end of the project, within 3 months by the closing of project activities (M36).

Data archiving at ZENODO: free of charge

Copyright licensing with Creative Commons: free of charge

7.2 Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in the project

Each beneficiary leading the Work Package is responsible for preparing the datasets to make FAIR the data collected within its own activities, provided that MfN, as Project Coordinator is co-responsible for general coordination and supervision. At least one responsible person from each WP involved in data collection activities (WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7) will be selected. It is up to the WP leader to decide whether to select only one responsible for the WP or one responsible for each partner organization involved in the WP. Responsible persons will be selected by the end of October 2019 (M10).

7.3 Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation

Data preservation of ten years after the project is required by the Grant Agreement. The associated costs for dataset preparation for archiving will be covered by the project itself. Long-term preservation will be provided and associated costs covered by the repository.

8 Data security

The EU-Citizen.Science project will ensure that any personal data collected throughout the activities of the project will be protected in a safe and secure way, in full compliance with GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) requirements, assuring privacy requirements and preventing improper use. For all data collected during any of the phases of the project (e.g. requirements analysis for the portal, evaluation data during events and trainings, etc.) the *principle of storage limitation* (Article 5 (e)) is obligatory, which states that personal data must be “kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed [...]”

To comply with this, the project partners storing personal data have identified and provided justification for the length of time any data they have gathered is stored, and for what purposes. EU-Citizen.Science, and especially the responsible project partners have to carefully consider all challenges for data storage, including deleting all data no longer required for the project, or at the request of the owner of that data. Project partners responsible for the data are therefore obliged to periodically review the data they hold and erase or anonymise it when no longer needed.

Project partners must define the period of retention of personal data and adopt a data retention policy in accordance with the purpose of the data. In addition, when the period of retention is identified, project partners will evaluate the appropriate actions to take in regards to anonymising or erasing the data that have been processed. All data collected during the project will be deleted at the end of the project (12/2021), with the exception of data and information that are relevant for the continuation of the platform, during the 5 year period that ECSA will take responsibility for maintaining the platform beyond the end of the project. At the point of handover to ECSA, a new Data Management Plan will be out in place. A detailed overview of the duration of storage of individual records in different work packages is part of the deliverable 1.1 Data Management Plan.

The following table on "Data relevance and Period of Storage" shows how long certain data is needed by the different work packages and which data is relevant for the EU-Citizen.Science platform beyond the duration of the project. These are specifically the contents of the platform developed in work package 3 (tools, guidelines and materials), and the data for the newsletter in work package 6.

	Type of Data	Relevance for the Project	Period of storing data
WP 1 (MfN)	Contact details of RIAs projects and other institutions (names, mails, addresses)	Enables to build a network of citizen science, mainstreaming and strengthening the community	Three years, duration of the project
WP 2 (ECSA)	Name, email address, job title, gender, IP addresses and other identifying details for analytics	Enables to build a network of citizen science, mainstreaming and	At least for the duration of the project (12/2021) plus five

		strengthening the community	years ECSA guarantees its continuity
WP 3 (IIASA)	Tools, guidelines, materials; Basic demographic data (e.g. names, email addresses, job titles, etc.) of the mentioned target groups to be added to the website when providing info on TGMs and best practices	As core objective the platform provides tools, guidelines and materials about Citizen Science addressing a broad variety of stakeholders/users, therefore the data collected in WP 3 is central for the implementation of the project	At least for the duration of the project (12/2021) plus five years ECSA guarantees its continuity
WP 4 (Earthwatch)	Email address	Enables the communication and dissemination about citizen science, identifying networks and establishing networks	At least for the duration of the project to keep subscribers updated on the platform developments. 2 years and beyond to allow people to keep record of their data
WP 5 (UCL)	Name, email address, job title, gender, IP addresses and other identifying details for learning analytics (behaviour on the training system) Informed consent will be integrated in the interface	Enables to identify the people who are using the training and being able to report on their characteristics for project reporting and evaluation Enables improvement of training material and training environment	At least for the 3 years of the project to keep subscribers updated on the platform developments. 2 years and beyond to allow people to keep record of their training.
WP 6 (ECSITE)	Contact details: Name, email address, organisation. Informed consent needed for the newsletter: GDPR. Link to the privacy policy of the project website. TGMs Training modules and all the content that will be developed during the project to disseminate its results and make them widely available Events/conferences on citizen science or where	Enables the communication and dissemination about the project and its results to the newsletter subscribers and relevant stakeholders.	At least for the 3 years of the project to keep subscribers updated on the project's developments, and possibly for 5 years more if people express their interest to be kept informed about the sustainable platform and its content.

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	EU-Citizen.Science will be presented & main contact person details		
WP 7 (ZSI)	Basic demographic data	Enables and supports internal evaluation and impact assessment	Three years, duration of the project and deleted at the end of the project (12/2021)

Table 4 Overview of WP, collected data, relevance and period of storage

Retention plans for the individual work packages are developed as part of the data management plan and are maintained and updated as a living document over the entire duration of the project. The decisions on the duration of storage take into account the following aspects:

- Considering the purposes for processing the personal data
- Considering whether you need to keep a record of a relationship with the individual once that relationship ends. You may not need to delete all personal data when the relationship ends.
- Considering whether you need to keep information to defend possible future legal claims.
- Considering any legal or regulatory requirements.

The data is stored in secure locations. The project partners, who are responsible for data collection and processing, determine the data storage location in accordance with the data protection guidelines. A detailed overview of what data is stored where by which partner is an integral part of the Data Management Plan developed as Deliverable 1.1. See therefore chapter 10 Dataset in EU-Citizen.Science project on page 34.

On the confidentiality and integrity of the treatment of data, GDPR Article 5(f), saying that personal data should be processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures (*‘principle of integrity and confidentiality’*).

Engagement in the platform involves personal data collection and processing. Formalized questionnaires and data will be stored at the local level and pseudo-/ anonymization will be applied. Every subject name will be replaced by a unique study number (ID code). The data warehouse at the end of the study will eventually be made publicly accessible after a process of anonymization. The following procedures will be included in the research protocol to safeguard the privacy of study subjects:

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- Reported study results will pertain to analyses of aggregate data. No individual's name will be associated with any published or unpublished report of this study;
- Personal information, including questionnaires, will be safely stored locally in secure facilities, and names will be replaced by unique study members – ID code stored separately. Primary databases and analysis files will be stored on computers with personal identifiers removed. In each of the centers, a person will be appointed as responsible for the data, and they will coordinate with the project Data Manager.
- ID will link all basic data required for the study and will be stored in password protected computer files. Access to these files will be limited to authorized project personnel.
- In the case that participants will provide their contact details (telephone, email-address) after having given their consent to participating and having agreed to be re-contacted for research purposes, this information will be stored in password protected computer files. Access to these files will be limited to authorized project personnel, whose names will be communicated to participants.
- Hard copy records or computer-generated records containing personally identifiable information will be stored in locked cabinets in an office with limited access.
- The project personnel will be informed of the importance of confidentiality of individual records and required to sign a confidentiality agreement.

The Project Handbook (D1.2) will describe in detail how EU-Citizen.Science intends to handle privacy and security issues. Allowing an appropriate view to RRI the project will develop several activities around a reflective RRI process for all its stakeholders, summarized within the Project Handbook. The aim of the RRI aspects in the handbook is to raise the awareness of the RRI concept and its implication for the day-to-day work in the project and acting accordingly. In practice, this adapted RRI approach will be put in place by training material provided by the project. In addition, EU-Citizen.Science will continuously follow up an approach that insures an appropriate level of ethical sensitivity, meaning that any changes and implementations will be viewed from an ethical perspective and (if needed) actions taken accordingly.

During the project duration, the data are accessible in different types and levels. At this point we distinguish three stages of publication in the project: First, data available to the whole consortium (consisting of 14 project partners), such as the visual identities and the minutes of the meetings. Second, data that is only accessible to the responsible project partners, e.g. data from questionnaires or interviews. Both variants concerning restrictive access functioning via password-protected servers. Third, data and information made publicly available, such as most of the deliverables created in the project.

Personal data such as individual questionnaire responses, mail addresses etc will be stored by partners in locked cabinets and shredded at the end of the project. During the project regular data backups will be taken. For each dataset a responsible partner has been identified who will be responsible for ensuring everyone involved in the data is aware of their individual responsibilities.

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9 Ethical aspects

Deliverables 8.1, D8.2, D8.3, and D8.4 cover the ethics requirements in connection with the main issues of data management within the project. These documents will be regularly updated by the project coordinator in collaboration with the work package leaders and the members of the Executive Board. It is therefore a living document, which will be processed until the end of the project period.

Executive Summary of each Deliverable

Deliverable 8.1 H-POPD - Requirement No. 1 focusing on the requirements of the European Commission regarding informed consent for collecting and processing of data throughout the EU-Citizen.Science project. We therefore developed an Information Sheet and Informed Consent.

Deliverable 8.2 POPD - Requirement No. 2 is mainly about the data minimisation principle and how this will be implemented within the EU-Citizen.Science project.

Deliverable 8.3 POPD - Requirement No. 3 focuses on the requirements of the European Commission regarding the publication of research data, such as scientific publications, that will be produced in the framework of the collaborative project.

Deliverable 8.4 POPD - Requirement No. 4 focuses on the organizational and technical measurements the project implements to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data and research participants. It contains detailed information on the procedure for data collection, storage, protection and destruction.

10 Dataset in EU-Citizen.Science project

Dataset name and Outline of Data	Institution in Charge	Work Packages
DS_EU-CITSCI_1_Project_Partner This dataset consists of consortium members, advisory board members	MfN	1
DS_EU-CITSCI_2_Involves_Participants This dataset consists of subscribers to mailing list and participants to events	MfN/ ECSITE	1/6
DS_EU-CITSCI_3_Project_Output This dataset consists of project outputs, such as deliverables, which are not research data, but is included within this organisation of data due to reasons of completeness.	MFN	1
DS_EU-CITSCI_4_Stakeholder_Mapping This dataset consists of information about Stakeholders, key networks and platform-community members.	ECSA	2
DS_EU-CITSCI_5_User_Expectations This dataset consists of user expectations concerning the platform EU-Citizen.Science.	ECSA	2
DS_EU-CITSCI_6_TGMs This dataset consists of tools, guidelines and materials (TGMs) on citizen science.	IIASA	3
DS_EU-CITSCI_7_Policy_Recommendation This dataset consists of guidelines and recommendations for policy makers.	Earthwatch	4
DS_EU-CITSCI_8_Training_Moduls This dataset consists of materials and data on training modules.	UCL	5
DS_EU-CITSCI_9_Communication This dataset consists of communication and dissemination materials.	ECSITE	6
DS_EU-CITSCI_10_Evaluation_Impact_Assessment This dataset consists of data about validation of the projects impact at multi levels.	ZSI	7

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10.1 Datasets Details

DS_EU-CITSCI_1_Project_Partner

Type of Data	Description	Access mechanism	Working Format	Primary Storage during Project	Access during project C=Consortium P=responsible partner O= open access	Backup/ security during Project	Preserved after project? Y=all data S=representative sample N=no data X=selected examples may be used in other data, but source not preserved	Preserved format	Volume to be reserved	Access after project
Contacts database	List of project partner, members of consortium, members of advisory board, third parties	Excel	Xls	Central Drive	C	MFN	N	-	-	-

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DS_EU-CITSCI_2_Involveses_Participants

Type of Data	Description	Access mechanism	Working Format	Primary Storage during Project	Access during project C=Consortium P=responsible partner O= open access	Backup/ security during Project	Preserved after project? Y=all data S=representative sample N=no data X=selected examples may be used in other data, but source not preserved	Preserved format	Volume to be preserved	Access after project
Contacts database	List of subscribers, including event attendees, participants, contributors. (all with consent given)	Excel	Xls	Central Drive	C	MFN	N	-	-	-

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DS_EU-CITSCI_3_Project_Output

Type of Data	Description	Access mechanism	Working Format	Primary Storage during Project	Access during project C=Consortium P=responsible partner O= open access	Backup/ security during Project	Preserved after project? Y=all data S=representative sample N=no data X=selected examples may be used in other data, but source not preserved	Preserved format	Volume to be preserved	Access after project
project deliverables	Formal deliverable from project	WORD	DOC	Relevant WP, central drive	C	P	Y	PDF		unrestricted
Academic publication	Academic publication arising from EU-Citizen.Science	WORD	DOC	Relevant WP, central drive	P	P	Y	PDF		unrestricted
Dissemination record	Record of dissemination events	Excel	Xls	Relevant WP, central drive	C	P	Y	PDF		unrestricted

DS_EU-CITSCI_4_Stakeholder_Mapping

Type of Data	Description	Access mechanism	Working Format	Primary Storage during Project	Access during project C=Consortium P=responsible partner O= open access	Backup/ security during Project	Preserved after project? Y=all data S=representative sample N=no data X=selected examples may be used in other data, but source not preserved	Preserved format	Volume to be preserved	Access after project
List of stakeholders	Table listing target stakeholders (groups / individuals) across EU	Table in D2.1 (Word)	DOC	Relevant WP, central drive	C	P	Y	PDF	-	Internal

Type of Data	Description	Access mechanism	Working Format	Primary Storage during Project	Access during project C=Consortium P=responsible partner O= open access	Backup/security during Project	Preserved after project? Y=all data S=representative sample N=no data X=selected examples may be used in other data, but source not preserved	Preserved format	Volume to be preserved	Access after project
Text files	This dataset consists of transcripts of interviews, meeting notes and survey data .	Excel and Word	xls, doc, GDoc, Gsheet	Relevant WP, central drive	C	P	Y	Textual and spreadsheet formats		Internal

Type of Data	Description	Access mechanism	Working Format	Primary Storage during Project	Access during project C=Consortium P=responsible partner O= open access	Backup/security during Project	Preserved after project? Y=all data S=representative sample N=no data X=selected examples may be used in other data, but source not preserved	Preserved format	Volume to be preserved	Access after project
Citizen Science TGMs	TGMs could be written texts, guidelines, diagrams, online toolkits, websites, videos, podcasts, software tools, etc. on citizen science	any format	any format	EU-Citizen.Science platform	O	P	Y	any format		unrestricted

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DS_EU-CITSCI_7_Policy_Recommendation

Type of data	Description	Access mechanism	Working Format	Primary Storage during Project	Access during project C=Consortium P=responsible partner O=open access	Backup/security during Project	Preserved after project? Y=all data S=representative sample N=no data X=selected examples may be used in other data, but source not preserved	Preserved format	Volume to be preserved	Access after project
Text files	This dataset consists of guidelines and recommendations for policy makers.	EU-Citizen. Science platform	Any textual format	EU-Citizen. Science platform and OneDrive	O	OneDrive backup and security	Y	Textual format	3 GB	Unrestricted

Type of Data	Description	Access mechanism	Working Format	Primary Storage during Project	Access during project C=Consortium P=responsible partner O= open access	Backup/security during Project	Preserved after project? Y=all data S=representative sample N=no data X=selected examples may be used in other data, but source not preserved	Preserved format	Volume to be preserved	Access after project
Training Modules created by EU-Citizen.Science	Many formats including text files, multimedia video	EU-Citizen.Science platform	any format	EU-Citizen.Science platform	O	C	Y	any format		unrestricted
Training Modules produced by external third parties	Many formats including text files, multimedia video. Meta data will be textual	EU-Citizen.Science platform	any format	meta data on the platform	O	C	only links and meta data are preserved	meta data		-

Type of Data	Description	Access mechanism	Working Format	Primary Storage during Project	Access during project C=Consortium P=responsible partner O= open access	Backup/ security during Project	Preserved after project? Y=all data S=representative sample N=no data X=selected examples may be used in other data, but source not preserved	Preserved format	Volume to be preserved	Access after project
Contacts database	List of subscribers (all with consent given)	Excel	Xls	Mailchimp & local secure server	P	P	N	-	-	-
Social media reports	Followers & reach	Graphs & Excel	XLs	Twitter, Facebook, Instagram & local secure server	P and C	P	Y			unrestricted
Dissemination spreadsheet	Excel sheet with data on organised events used for communication & dissemination	Excel	xls	Central drive	C	C	N			

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Multimedia	Citizen science pictures and videos shared by the C and partners for the communication	png, jpg, mp4, etc.		Central drive and local secure server	P and C	P	S			
Deliverable	Report on the project's communication and dissemination activities	Word	Doc	Central drive & local secure server	C	C	Y	PDF		unrestricted

Type of Data	Description	Access mechanism	Working Format	Primary Storage during Project	Access during project C=Consortium P=responsible partner O= open access	Backup/security during Project	Preserved after project? Y=all data S=representative sample N=no data X=selected examples may be used in other data, but source not preserved	Preserved format	Volume to be preserved	Access after project
Interviews	Interviews with selected participants of events and trainings	WORD MAXQDA	DOC MX18	ZSI-Server	P	P	N		-	internal
Questionnaires	Questionnaires to selected participants of events and trainings	Excel LimeSurvey	xls	ZSI-Server	P	P	N		-	internal
Walkthrough	Combination of think aloud protocol and interview	WORD	DOC	ZSI-Server	P	P	N		-	internal

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Feedback Cards	Postcards with mini-questionnaire	Excel	xls	Central Drive	C	C	N		-	internal
Dissemination spreadsheet	Excel sheet with data on organised events used for evaluation too	Excel	xls	Central drive	C	C	N		-	internal

11 Conclusion

This Data Management Plan identifies the data that is planned to be stored during and after the EU-Citizen.Science project. It will need revision as the project progresses and the value of data collected is evaluated, alongside decisions to collect additional data. The identification of a suitable data repository is the project's next priority; once this has been identified, the DMP will be revisited and revised accordingly to the requirements of the repository.

12 References

European Commission, 2016. Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020.

[Online], available at:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf [accessed 24 Mai 2019]

European Commission, 2016. Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020 v3.1 [Online], available at:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf [accessed 7 Mai 2019]

Annex 1 – Metadata to be recorded against each Dataset

Each WP folder in the central drive should contain a doc file with the following information:

Project Name	EU-Citizen.Science
Principal Investigator	Katrin Vohland
Project Description	EU-Citizen.Science is a project supported by the European Commission under its Horizon 2020 programme – Science with and for Society. The project will develop and maintain an innovative, collaborative online hub that will serve as the centrepiece for bringing together a vibrant European Citizen Science community. This shared online exchange and learning space will transform the way that citizen science projects are conceived and developed, encourage and support citizen science novices, practitioners, participants and institutions equally to exchange experiences, successful strategies and to jointly advance the role and recognition of citizen science in the European context. The EU-Citizen.Science project will take stock of the vast amount of existing tools, guidelines and other materials available in and for citizen science, to highlight, curate and organize high-quality contents for an ever growing and diversifying group of interested parties.
Founding sources	Horizon 2020
Responsible Organisation	Partner Name
Contact Person	Partner Contact Name
Contact Email	Partner Email
Data Overview	Dataset description as given by this document
Technical Information of Files	For qualitative data, description and format of each element
Coding instrument	The name of the mechanism for accessing files
Data Collection Start Date	
Data Collection End Date	

Confidentiality Classification	Confidential/Public
Data Subject	Events/Methodology/Technology/People
Keywords	List of Keywords

Annex 2 – Creative Common Licence

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